

ANALYSES OF THE DEPENDENT CLAUSE IN ASYNDETTIC COMPOUND SENTENCES

Syntax

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Abstract

The given article presents the views on the dependent clause in asyndetic compound sentences and their broad variants of usage. The semantic relations between the components of the asyndetic compound sentences are shown, where the second component directly defines the meaning of the first component of the sentences. The classification of semantic relations between the two components of asyndetic compound sentences with dependent clause in the Uzbek language is presented by examples. Furthermore, the syntactic functions of the subordinate clause in the asyndetic compound sentences are also the matter of investigations.

One of the substantial matters in linguistics is to define the relations between the form and the content and their responding regularities, which is also essential in investigating the compound sentences.

The theory of the compound sentences has been broadly investigated in Uzbek linguistics. We can cite the wide range works of the following researchers as the academician G. Abdukhmanov, M. Askarova, A. Berdialiev, A. Nurmonov, N. Mahkmudov, A. Mamajonov [1, 2, 3, 7, 5, 4].

The compound syntactic unit with two or more semantically connected predicative units, which are joined only by means of melody without any grammatical connectives, is considered a compound sentence [1].

For lack of the grammatical connectives in the relations of more than one predicative unit the role of the melody and lexical means is increasing. The use of some of the lexical means, the existence of the dependent clauses of sentences, the repetition of some parts of speech in both predicative units, the use of subordinate or dependent clauses serve as the main means in connecting the parts of the asyndetic compound sentences and in defining their semantic relations.

The melody is the main means of connecting in the compound sentences, because the melody fulfils the function of defining the various shades of the meaning of the sentences [5]. The parts of the asyndetic compound sentences identify the meaning in different ways, containing the definite parallelism in the parts of the sentences and grammatical constructions, which is called subordinative asyndetic compound sentence.

The situation or event, realized in one of the parts of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence is related to the second part, or in other words, one part of the sentence explains and completes the other one.

The second predicative unit as the composite part of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence defines the first predicative unit in different ways. Mainly, the second predicative unit defines the meaning of some parts of the first predicative unit, determines the general content of the first part in different syntactic positions and identifies the information through this meaning.

Example 1. *Hammaning tilida shu savol, lekin hammaning dilida ezgu bir tilak: "Iloyim, tengi topilsin! "Muhayyo" A.Qahhor. 2. Bular bir-ikki yil binoyidek turmush qilishdi, keyin Javlon qiliq chiqardi: bir joyda ko'p ishlamaydigan, tez-tez ichadigan, xotin-xalajga aylanishadigan bo'ldi. "Muhabbat" A.Qahhor.*

As it is seen, the second predicative unit defines the meaning of the first predicative unit in the asyndetic compound sentence.

The parts of the asyndetic compound sentences are defined by the verb, pronoun and abstract noun. The part with the defined meaning of the asyndetic compound sentence is placed in the first part of the sentence and is distinguished from the other parts of the sentence by stress. The predicative unit with subordinate clause is uttered in high pitch and has a pause, which keeps the sign of the beginning of the second predicative unit.

The dependent clause in asyndetic compound sentences can fulfill the function of different parts of speech.

The second predicate unit in the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence, defining the meaning of some parts of the first predicative unit is equal to the meaning of the defined part and according to the function is equal to the function of the defined subordinate clause. Thus, this part of the compound sentence can be syntactically substituted for the defined part.

Example 1. *Ota-bola hamon o'sha kiyimda edi: boshida cho'qqisimon qalpoq, egnida olimpiyka. "Tushda kechgan umrlar" O'.Hoshimov. 2. Qotilni hech kim bilmaydi. Ammo menga bir narsa aniq: Mendayin baxti qaro qiz yo'qdir boshqa Bu yorug' olamda. "Bug'uga aylangan qiro'l" T.Malik*

While the words "ўша" and "бир нарса" in the given subordinate asyndetic composite sentences are withdrawn, the second predicative units are used instead of them, changing the compound sentences into simple ones.

Example 1. *Ota-bola hamon boshida cho'qqisimon qalpoq, egnida olimpiyka kiyimida edi. 2. Qotilni hech kim bilmaydi. Ammo menga bu yorug' olamda mendan boshqa baxti qaro qiz yo'qligi aniq.*

It is obvious from the abovementioned, that the second part of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentences fulfills the syntactic function for the first part. Thus, the second part can fulfill the function of the subject, predicate, object, attribute and adverbial modifier towards the first part. It is worth mentioning that the second part of the compound sentence can answer the question of the subordinate clause in the first part.

Subsequently, the second part of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence can be classified as:

I. the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence, which has the subjective connection with the first part;

II. the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence, which has the objective connection with the first part;

III. the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence, which has the attributive connection with the first part;

IV. the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence, which has the relative connection with the first part.

I. In the sentences of the first type the second predicative unit defines the meaning of the subject in the subordinate clause.

Example 1. *Ofitser deganning bitta-yu bitta huquqi bor: u ham bo'lsa buyruqni bajarish! "Tushda kechgan umrlar" O'.Hoshimov* 2. *Otalarimizdan qolgan yaxshi an'ana bor: odamlar qasam ichib aka-uka tutinishadi. "Bug'uga aylangan qirol" T.Malik*

This type of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence has two forms:

1. The meaning of the subject, expressed through the subordinate clause in the first part is defined by the second sentence.

Example 1. *Uning qalbida bir ishonch nish urgan: qachonlardir butun bir xalq uchun foyda keltira oladigan ish qilish imkoni tug'iladi. "Nomus va qasos" T.Malik* 2. *Ammo menga bir narsa ochiq-oydindir: Siz avvalgi qirol emassiz. Sizdagi o'zgarishdan mening aqlim lol! "Bug'uga aylangan qirol" T.Malik*

The subject of the first predicative unit in this type of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentences is a subordinate clause *нарса*¹, which can be used with its own attributes as *бир нарса, икки нарса, шу нарса, ҳамма нарса*².

¹ thing

² a thing, two things, this thing, all things.

Example 1. *Uch narsa xotirani ziyoda etadi va safroni ketkazadi: misvok ishlatish, ro'za tutish va Qur'on tilovat qilish. Ali ibn Abu Tolib* 2. *Insof bilan aytganda, do'konda odamning jonidan bo'lak hamma narsa bor: yugoslav sigaretidan tortib yapon magnitofonlarigacha, yaltiroq "sim" ro'moldan tortib shoda-shoda durlargacha... "Tushda kechgan umrlar" O'.Hoshimov*

The use of the subordinate clause *narsa* with the attributes intensifies the abstractness of the subordinate clause and requires the definition. The second part of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence defines the meaning of the subordinate clause.

Example 1. *Ikki narsa kishi qo'lida bo'lsa uvol: go'zallikka mag'rur bo'lgan kishiga berilgan husn, ikkinchisi – go'zallik qadrini bilmaydigan kishiga tushib qolgan ayol. Xurramiy* 2. *Shundagina bir narsa shuurimga yetdi: "dux" o'zbekcha gapirayotgan edi. "Tushda kechgan umrlar" O'.Hoshimov*

2. The subject in the subordinate clause of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence can be omitted in some cases. In this way, the first predicative unit of the compound sentence can be one-member predicative unit.

Example 1. *Tadqiqotlarimizdan yana ma'lum bo'lishicha, jahl va adovat qondagi yallig'lanish bilan bog'liq oqsillarni ishlab chiqishni ham boshlab yuborishi mumkin. "Ma'rifat sadosi" gazetasidan* 2. *- Men hech kimni qarg'amayman, - dedi Qurbonoy xola ishonch bilan. – Qur'onda bitilgan: Alloh har narsani ko'rguvchidir. Tangrim hammasini ko'rib turibdi. "Tushda kechgan umrlar" O'.Hoshimov*

II. In the sentences of the second type, where the subordinate clause has an objective connection with the first part, the second predicative unit can define and complete the meaning or explain the meaning of the abstract notion in the subordinate clause [1]. As usual, the subordinate clause in the first predicative unit has the function of the object.

Example 1. *Har kuni bir gapni aytadi, to'yingni o'tkazaveramiz, dadang omon-esson kelsalar orzu-havaslarini nevara to'yidan ko'raveradilar, deydi.* 2. *Keyin to'satdan bir yangilikni angladim: o'zimda ro'y bergan o'zgarishni sezdim: ko'nglimdagi xavotir hissi yo'qola boshladi. Men o'z yurtimdaman. "Tushda kechgan umrlar" O'.Hoshimov*

The second part of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence, which is in objective relations to the first part, serves to complete the meaning of the first predicative unit in order to understand and realize the information of the definite event, the spiritual state of the person and to define the meaning of the subordinate clause.

Being in the objective relations to the first part, the second part of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence has the following relations to the first predicative unit:

1. The information about the definite event and situation.
2. Realization of the event.

3. The process of thought, the spiritual state of the person.

1. The second predicative unit in the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence presents the information about the event and situation in the first predicative unit, giving the supposed meaning and completing it.

The predicate of the first predicative unit of the asyndetic compound sentence is defined by the following verbs *aytmoq, so'ramoq, takrorlamoq, javob bermoq, qaytarmoq, yozmoq, va'da bermoq, ogohlantirmoq, talab qilmoq* (say, ask, repeat, answer, write, promise, warn, demand).

Example 1. *Har bir tong yorishadigan kun borki, inson bolasiga nido qiladi: "Men yangi yaraldim. Ishlaringga shohidman, mendan foydalanib qol."* Hasan Basriy 2. *Yerga qadam bosishim bilan Xayriddin ogohlantirdi: – Bismillo, deng, jo'ra! Bu tuproqda ajdodlarimiz yotibdi. "Tushda kechgan umrlar" O'.Hoshimov*

This type of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence can be in the form of the reported speech. The author's speech can be placed before, in the middle or after the reported speech.

Example 1. *Xudo sizdan marhamatini ayamaydi, - u shunday deb tiz cho'kdi-da, iltijo qildi: - Meni sotib qo'ymaslikka so'z bering. "Nomus va qasos" T.Malik 2. Ayasi bir gapni qayta-qayta takrorlardi: - Dadangda gunoh yo'q, bolam! Dadang – farishtadek toza odam. "Tushda kechgan umrlar" O'.Hoshimov*

2. The predicate of the first predicative unit in the subordinate asyndetic compound sentence, where the content of the subordinate clause is to realize the event and situation, is expressed by the verbs *bilmoq, ishonmoq, ko'rmoq, qaramoq, eshitmoq, eslamoq, tanimoq, tushuntirmoq* (know, believe, see, look, hear, remember, recognize, understand).

Example 1. *Qurbonoy ayvon o'rtasida to'xtab qolgan "shapkali"ning niyati nimaligiga aqli yetmas, hamon qo'rquvdan yuragi gursillab urar, faqat bir narsani aniq bilar edi: bu yomon odam. Dadasini olib ketgan. "Tushda kechgan umrlar" O'.Hoshimov 2. Gabo taslim bo'lmaydi. – Menga qara, pristav, ingushlar, sizlar ham eshitinglar: mening sizlarga qarshi hech qanday yomon niyatim yo'q. "Nomus va qasos" T.Malik*

The second predicative unit of this type of the asyndetic compound sentence presents what is realized from the first predicative unit.

3. The second predicative unit in the third type of the asyndetic compound sentences illustrates the person's thought and the spiritual state. Accordingly, the predicate of the first predicative unit is expressed by the verbs of the thought and spiritual state.

Example 1. *Men ishonaman, kelajak nasllar bugungi avlod tomonidan amalga oshirilgan ana shunday buyuk ishlarni minnatdorlik bilan eslaydi, biz boshlagan ishlarni, albatta, munosib davom ettiradi. Sh.M.Mirziyoyev*

2. *Bundan tashqari men butun vujudim bilan bir narsani aniq his qilib yotardim: ayni choqda oramizda, kechagi qo'rqoq bilan, qo'rqoqligi uchun o'rtoqlari tomonidan haydalgan o'sha qo'rqoq bilan uning orasida kurash, hayot-mamot jangi borardi. "Ma'suma" T.Malik*

III. The second predicative unit in the subordinate asyndetic composite sentence has attributive connections with the first predicative unit, specifying the meaning of the subordinate clause.

The second predicative unit of this type of the sentences defines the meaning of the nouns, clarifying the thought of the first predicative unit.

Example 1. *Qat'iy qoida bor: afg'on mashinalari katta yo'ldan qorong'ida yurishi taqiqlangan. "Tushda kechgan umrlar" O'.Hoshimov* 2. *Ilmda esa – balandi zirvali tog'lar haqida shunday bir ilm ham bor – uni yo'lbarsli turkumiga, mushuksimonlar oilasiga mansub, qorli Tiyonshon yo'lbarisi deb ataladi. "Qulayotgan tog'lar" Ch.Aytmatov*

The noun in the subordinate clause can be used not in isolation, but with its attribute. In this way, the meaning of the subordinate clause is exaggerating.

Example 1. *Dunyodagi eng mash'um va eng dahshatli voqea sodir bo'ldi: u qonsiragan muhabbati yo'lida vafoni, qallig'iga bo'lgan sadoqatini qurbon qildi. "Nomus va ajal" T.Malik.*

2. *Ha, meni, eng avvalo, uning buyumlari hayratga soldi: tilla suvi yugurtirilgan kumush zirak, taqib yurishga nomus qiladigan, almisoqdan qolgan medalyon, xullas, bir chaqaga qimmat buyumlar. "Ma'suma" T.Malik.*

In some cases this type of the asyndetic compound sentences can turn into the complex sentence.

Example. *Uning mardona turishi yigitlik jasorati, Qofqaz botirlari go'zalligining timsoli edi: yelkaları keng, baland bo'yli, qomati kelishgan, qora papog'i sal orqaga tashlangan, keng peshonasi ochiq, ko'zlari jonsarak. "Nomus va qasos" (T.Malik).*

IV. In the sentences of the relative connections of the second predicative unit with the first one the subordinate clause fulfills the syntactic function of the adverbial modifier and is expressed by pronoun and adverb.

The "шундай"(such) adverbial modifier in the subordinate clause can be substituted by "бундай(such)" and "қандай"(which). "Бундай" subordinate clause is differentiated from the subordinate clause "шундай" by exactness.

Example. *Qaytishda tag'in o'sha tartib yo'lga tushdik: boshlovchi tank, yukini bo'shatgan benzavozlar, BTR, yukini almashtirgan KamAZlar, BMP, yana KamAZlar, bizning tank, ortimizda ikkita BMP... "Tushda kechgan umrlar" (O'.Hoshimov).*

The adverbial modifier in the subordinate clause in the given type of the compound sentence can be omitted; however, the meaning of the second predicative unit can elucidate what subordinate clause is omitted.

Example. *Marg'uba yog'och panjaraning darchasidan boshini tiqib, salom yo'q, alik yo'q, (shunday deb) sayrab ketdi: "Megajin qizingizni yig'ishtirib olasizmi, yo'qmi! Bitta yigitning shohini sindirganlaring yetmasmidi, endi mening jiyanim qoldimi!.. Go'ristonda qo'ymasa, ko'chada qo'ymasa!.."* (Muhabbat" A.Qahhor)

We can come to the following conclusion from the abovementioned theoretical arguments and examples that the matter of the subordinate asyndetic compound sentences is quite essential and worth further profound considerations. It shows the broad use of the syntactic structure of the Uzbek language, which is of paramount scientific and practical importance.

References

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